

PACE / NutriPROGRAM Analysis Plan
Maternal vegetarian/plant-based diets and cord blood DNA methylation

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Background

Vegetarianism is becoming increasingly popular worldwide¹. Following vegetarian/plant-based diets during pregnancy has been associated with lower birth weight and small for gestational age offspring²⁻⁴. Although inconclusive, some evidence also suggests an association with other neonatal outcomes, such as neural tube defects and hypospadias^{2 5}. However, the molecular mechanisms underlying such associations are not well understood.

DNA methylation (DNAm) has been found to be related to fetal and neonatal health outcomes⁶, and some key nutrient intakes (e.g., iron, folates, and omega-3 fatty acids) and other nutrition-related factors (e.g., body mass index [BMI]) associated with DNAm⁶⁻¹⁰ tend to differ between vegetarians and non-vegetarians¹¹. Therefore, we hypothesise that changes in DNAm might be a possible mechanism between maternal vegetarian/plant-based diets and offspring health.

Aim

This epigenome-wide association study (EWAS) aims to examine cord blood DNAm in relation to maternal adherence to vegetarian and plant-based diets during pregnancy. In addition to single cytosine-phosphate-guanine (CpG) site analyses, we will also analyse differentially methylated regions (DMRs), which can be more statistically powerful and potentially more biologically relevant.

Eligibility

Your study is eligible if it fits into BOTH criteria below:

- It has epigenome-wide DNAm data measured in cord blood.
- It has maternal dietary data collected during pregnancy (e.g., from food frequency questionnaires [FFQ], 24-hour dietary recall [24HR], or food diaries). Eligible studies will be further categorised into two tiers:
 - **Tier 1:** With dietary data that can be used to derive both weekly intake frequencies (as times/week) and daily intakes (as grams/day) of the 18 food groups listed in **Table 1** below (see detailed information about each food group in **Supplementary Table 1**). Tier 1 studies will participate in the analyses for both vegetarianism and plant-based diet indices (see sections below).
 - **Tier 2:** With dietary data that can be used to derive weekly intake frequencies (as times/week) of 4 key food groups: meat, fish/seafood, egg, and dairy (**Table 1**). Tier 2 studies will participate in the analyses for vegetarianism only.

Please note:

- The exposures of interest used in this project MUST be derived from dietary data; studies with only self-defined vegetarianism data (typically collected using a single question like “Are you a vegetarian/vegan?” or “Are you following a vegetarian/vegan diet?”) are NOT eligible.
- Tier 2 analyses, with looser inclusion criteria, are for those studies using non-quantitative FFQs or with one or more of the 18 food groups missing. Studies will participate in EITHER tier 1 OR tier 2 analyses based on their eligibility.
- We assume that studies with dietary data in grams/day would have available data in times/week as well. Please get in contact if this is NOT the case in your study.
- For tier 2 studies, although the necessary food groups are only meat and fish/seafood because different subgroups of vegetarianism will be combined for the final analysis (see sections below), we still wish to derive detailed subgroups and describe their distribution. If your study has data on meat and fish/seafood intakes but not egg or dairy intakes, please get in touch with us as it may still be eligible.

Table 1. Food groups for defining vegetarian subgroups^{3 12} and calculating plant-based diet indices¹³.

Food groups (N = 18 in total)	Vegetarian subgroups				Plant-based diet indices		
	Non-vegetarian	Pesco-vegetarian	Full vegetarian		PDI	hPDI	uPDI
			Lacto-ovo-vegetarian	Vegan			
Healthy plant food groups (N = 7)							
Whole grains	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	Positive scores ^d	Positive scores	Reverse scores ^e
Fruits	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	Positive scores	Positive scores	Reverse scores
Vegetables	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	Positive scores	Positive scores	Reverse scores
Nuts	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	Positive scores	Positive scores	Reverse scores
Legumes	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	Positive scores	Positive scores	Reverse scores
Vegetable oils ^a	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	Positive scores	Positive scores	Reverse scores
Tea and coffee	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	Positive scores	Positive scores	Reverse scores
Less healthy plant food groups (N = 5)							
Fruit juices	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	Positive scores	Reverse scores	Positive scores
Refined grains	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	Positive scores	Reverse scores	Positive scores
Potatoes	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	Positive scores	Reverse scores	Positive scores
Sugar-sweetened beverages	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	Positive scores	Reverse scores	Positive scores
Sweets and desserts	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	No restriction	Positive scores	Reverse scores	Positive scores
Animal food groups (N = 6)							
Animal fat ^b	-	-	-	-	Reverse scores	Reverse scores	Reverse scores
Dairy	No restriction	No restriction	≥1 time/mo	<1 time/mo	Reverse scores	Reverse scores	Reverse scores
Eggs	No restriction	No restriction			Reverse scores	Reverse scores	Reverse scores
Fish and seafood	No restriction	≥1 time/mo	Reverse scores		Reverse scores	Reverse scores	
Meat	No restriction	<1 time/mo	<1 time/mo	Reverse scores	Reverse scores	Reverse scores	
Miscellaneous animal-based foods ^c	-	-	-	-	Reverse scores	Reverse scores	Reverse scores

^aDefined as oils from plant sources that are liquid in room temperature.

^bDefined as fats from animal sources that are solid/semi-solid in room temperature; not considered in the definition of vegetarian subgroups.

^cDefined as foods containing animal-based content that cannot be classified into other animal food groups; not considered in the definition of vegetarian subgroups.

^dScores 1, 2, and 3 are assigned to the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd tertile of intake, respectively.

^eScores 3, 2, and 1 are assigned to the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd tertile of intake, respectively.

PDI, overall plant-based diet index; hPDI, healthful plant-based diet index; uPDI, unhealthful plant-based diet index.

Exclusions

- Please exclude twins and siblings (i.e., conduct a singleton-only analysis and include one child per family in case of multiple siblings from the same family).
- We do NOT require excluding participants of ethnicities other than European ancestry. If your study is multi-ethnic, please analyse different ethnicities separately (the suggested minimum sample size per ethnic group is 50). Please get in contact with us if you think the number of cases is too low in any ethnic group.

Adherence to vegetarian/plant-based diets

Our exposures of interest are maternal adherence to vegetarian and plant-based diets during pregnancy, including the following five variables:

- Two binary variables for vegetarianism – “veggie1” (i.e., full vegetarians vs. non-vegetarians) and “veggie2” (i.e., full vegetarians + pesco-vegetarians vs. non-vegetarians)^{3 12}
- Three continuous variables for the plant-based diet index (PDI) – overall PDI, healthful PDI (hPDI), and unhealthful PDI (uPDI)¹³. **Table 1** above summarises the definition of various vegetarian subgroups and the calculation of different versions of PDIs. More details can be found in **Supplementary Note 1**.

If your study has maternal dietary data measured at multiple time points throughout pregnancy, please get in touch.

Models

We will run linear regression models (from the “limma” R package) for our dietary exposures and neonatal DNAm outcomes.

Main analysis

There will be four models for each of the five exposures of interest:

- “veggie1”: full vegetarians vs. non-vegetarians (binary, with non-vegetarians as the reference group)
- “veggie2”: full vegetarians + pesco-vegetarians vs. non-vegetarians (binary, with non-vegetarians as the reference group)
- PDI (continuous, range 18 to 54)
- hPDI (continuous, range 18 to 54)
- uPDI (continuous, range 18 to 54)

Please note:

- Tier 2 studies will only participate in the analyses for “veggie1” and “veggie2”.
- Please get in touch if the number of cases in “veggie1” or “veggie2” is too low (e.g., <10).

Table 2 below presents a summary of the modelling process. Please adjust for as many covariates specified below as possible in each model and record if any of them are not adjusted for as required and why. The main model of interest will be the fully adjusted one. The “no-cells” and minimally adjusted models are being run because they are common practice and can help understand the effect of adjustments. The rationale for setting up the additional model is that nutrition-related factors (e.g., BMI, energy intake, dietary supplement use) may mediate the effect of diet on health outcomes, and this model can provide insights into the potential role of these factors. To avoid potential collider bias, we

will NOT consider gestational age at birth as a covariate because it is likely to be influenced by both maternal diet and other adjusted or unadjusted prenatal factors.

Table 2. Modelling for the association between maternal adherence to vegetarian/plant-based diets during pregnancy and cord blood DNA methylation.

	Maternal dietary exposures of interest				
	“veggie1”	“veggie2”	PDI	hPDI	uPDI
“No-cells” model Adjusted for child sex and batch (as surrogate variables) only	NoCellModel.veggie1	NoCellModel.veggie2	NoCellModel.PDI	NoCellModel.hPDI	NoCellModel.uPDI
Minimally adjusted model Additionally adjusted for blood cell types	MinModel.veggie1	MinModel.veggie2	MinModel.PDI	MinModel.hPDI	MinModel.uPDI
Fully adjusted model (Note: This is the “partially-adjusted model” in the EWAS manuscript) Additionally adjusted for maternal age, education attainment, parity, and maternal smoking during pregnancy	FullModel.veggie1	FullModel.veggie2	FullModel.PDI	FullModel.hPDI	FullModel.uPDI
Additional model (Note: This is the “fully-adjusted model” in the EWAS manuscript) Additionally adjusted for maternal pre-pregnancy BMI, total energy intake, and dietary supplementation during pregnancy.	AddModel.veggie1	AddModel.veggie2	AddModel.PDI	AddModel.hPDI	AddModel.uPDI

“veggie1” (full vegetarians vs. non-vegetarians) and “veggie2” (full vegetarians + pesco-vegetarians vs. non-vegetarians) are as binary variables, with non-vegetarians as the reference group.

PDI, hPDI, and uPDI are as continuous variables, ranging from 18 to 54.

PDI, overall plant-based diet index; hPDI, healthful plant-based diet index; uPDI, unhealthful plant-based diet index.

Sensitivity analyses

We will also conduct ethnic-specific analyses. We will re-run the meta-analysis in participants of European ancestry only. So please analyse different ethnicities separately if your study is multi-ethnic.

R Code

This analysis plan is accompanied by an R script (named as “**MatVegDiet_PACE_EWAS.r**”), which contains the functions necessary for preparing data and running the analyses. You will need to edit the code to tailor them to your study. In the script, sections that need to be edited are highlighted (see the “[**PLEASE CHANGE**]” notice). Before running the script, your phenotype data need to be set up correctly, with the correct variable column names, as explained in this analysis plan and the R script. The script also contains the code for deriving dietary exposure variables (i.e., vegetarian subgroups and PDIs).

If you have any questions or difficulties running the code or think you need to make extra changes to the script to suit your dataset, please do not hesitate to contact Peiyuan Huang (peiyuan.huang@bristol.ac.uk) and cc Gemma Sharp (g.c.sharp@exeter.ac.uk).

Inputs

In this study, maternal vegetarian/plant-based diets during pregnancy are always used as the exposure and DNAm in cord blood as the outcome. Before running the code, analysts need to prepare the following inputs:

- **A single phenotype file (including cell type data)** – containing a column called “sample.id” (used to match to the methylation matrix) and all phenotype data (including the dietary variables, covariates, and cell types). It is very important that variables in your phenotype data are named according to the guidelines set out in this document and R script. Please note that this will be a complete case analysis, so food intake tertiles for PDIs should be calculated in the final subset (i.e., those with non-missing data in exposure, outcome, and all covariates). The script will subset the samples to the complete cases before tertile calculation.
- **A methylation matrix** – with column names matched to “sample.id” in the phenotype file.

For the dietary variables, we will need the daily intake (in g/day) of each of the 18 food groups for deriving PDIs and the weekly intake frequency (in times/week) of each of the 4 key animal food groups (i.e., meat, fish/seafood, egg, and dairy) for classifying vegetarian subgroups.

Preparation of methylation data

This analysis uses methylation data (Illumina beta-values) from cord blood measured using either the EPIC or 450K Illumina arrays. Please prepare methylation matrices as follows:

- Normalise the beta-values using your preferred method and mention the method you chose in the attached “cohort info” Excel file.
- Please do NOT convert to M-values (i.e., logit transformation of beta-values).
- You can use your preferred study QC settings for probe filtering (e.g., removing probes with a high detection p-value, probes on sex chromosomes, and probes used as controls).

- However, if possible, please do NOT exclude probes identified as polymorphic sites based on the lists provided by Chen et al.¹⁴ or Naeem et al.¹⁵ (or similar). We will do this at the meta-analysis stage.
- The R script includes the code to remove outliers using the IQR*3 (Tukey) method. Please run these lines or use methylation data with outliers already removed using this method.
- The script includes the code to match your phenotype file to your methylation matrix, so you do NOT have to do this beforehand. However, the columns of your methylation matrix MUST be named according to a unique identifier, which is also used in your phenotype data under the column “sample.id”. If the methylation and the phenotype IDs in your study are not the same and you do not know how to set this up, please get in touch.

Batch

Please do NOT include a batch variable. The code provided calculates surrogate variables to adjust for technical variation. Please do NOT use ComBat or any other methods to adjust your beta matrix for batch before running the EWAS.

Cell types

Cord blood cell type estimation: Use the “Salas” reference set for cell type estimation in the “FlowSorted.CordBlood.Combined.450K” or “FlowSorted.CordBlood.Combined.EPIC” Bioconductor package for cell type correction. These packages include the following cell types: “CD8T”, “CD4T”, “NK”, “Bcell”, “Mono”, “Gran”, and “nRBC”.

Covariates

A complete list of covariates and variable names (as used in the phenotype file and R script) is provided in **Table 3** below.

Table 3. List of covariates and their variable names.

Variables	Values	Variable name
Child sex	Male = 0 Female = 1	sex
Maternal age at delivery (or conception)	Continuous (years)	mat.age
Highest level of maternal education at the time of delivery (or shortly after) – Please use your preferred definition in your study.	Lower = 0 Higher = 1	mat.edu
Mother’s parity (number of previous pregnancies)	No previous delivery = 0 At least 1 previous delivery = 1	mat.parity
Sustained maternal smoking during pregnancy	No smoking or quit in the first trimester = 0 Sustained smoking throughout pregnancy = 1	mat.smoking
Maternal pre-pregnancy BMI (pre-pregnancy is preferred, but BMI at the early stage of pregnancy is also fine)	Continuous (kg/m ²)	mat.bmi
Maternal total energy intake during pregnancy ^a	Continuous (kcal/day)	mat.kcal
Maternal dietary supplementation during pregnancy ^b	No supplement use at any time points during pregnancy = 0 At least 1 type of supplement used at any time point during pregnancy (preferably occurring before or at the same time as dietary assessment) = 1	mat.suppl

^aEstimated from maternal dietary data during pregnancy.

^bBased on available information in each study; can be any type of supplement (e.g., in ALSPAC, this includes iron, zinc, calcium, folic acid, multivitamins, and “other”; omega-3 fatty acids may also be considered if available in your study).

Output format (how to share the results with us)

The code provided will generate the output files we want and name them accordingly. Please double-check that the initial parameters are set up as follows:

- [PROJECT]: Project name, which is **MatVegDiet** for this project
- [STUDY]: Your study name (e.g., **ALSPAC**)
- [EXPOSURE]: **veggie1 / veggie2 / PDI / hPDI / uPDI**
- [MODEL]: **NoCellModel / MinModel / FullModel / AddModel**
- [TIMEPOINT]: The time point at which methylation data were measured, which is **birth** for this project
- [DATE]: The date when the analysis is performed (in the format “YYYYMMDD”, e.g., **20221130**); the R code will generate this automatically

Please supply the following output files in the specified formats (these are automatically created using the supplied R script):

- Rdata files (5 for tier 1 studies, 2 for tier 2 studies) for EWAS results, each containing outputs from all four EWAS models for one exposure variable, named as: “[PROJECT].[STUDY].[EXPOSURE].EWASres.[TIMEPOINT].[DATE].Rdata” (e.g., “MatVegDiet.ALSPAC.veggie1.EWASres.birth.20221130.Rdata”).
- One Rdata files for the log of the IQR*3 (Tukey) method, named as: “[PROJECT].[STUDY].logIQR.[TIMEPOINT].[DATE].Rdata”.
- One csv file showing the distribution of the 18 food groups, named as: “[PROJECT].[STUDY].food.group.distribute.[TIMEPOINT].[DATE].csv”. Not applicable for tier 2 studies.
- One csv file showing the tertile cutoffs of the 18 food groups, named as: “[PROJECT].[STUDY].food.group.tertile.[TIMEPOINT].[DATE].csv”. Not applicable for tier 2 studies.
- One csv file showing summary statistics of phenotype data, named as: “[PROJECT].[STUDY].tableone.[TIMEPOINT].[DATE].csv”.
- One csv file showing the intake of each available food group by vegetarian subgroups, named as: “[PROJECT].[STUDY].ByVegDiet.[TIMEPOINT].[DATE].csv”.
- One correlogram showing the correlation matrix between PDIs and intakes of the 18 food groups, named as: “[PROJECT].[STUDY].correlogram.[TIMEPOINT].[DATE].png”. Not applicable for tier 2 studies.
- Three histograms for PDI, hPDI, and uPDI, named as: “[PROJECT].[STUDY].[EXPOSURE].histogram.[TIMEPOINT].[DATE].jpg”. Not applicable for tier 2 studies.
- Q-Q plots (20 for tier 1 studies, 8 for tier 2 studies) – Separate plots will be created for each exposure variable and model, named as: “[PROJECT].[STUDY].[MODEL].[EXPOSURE].QQ.[TIMEPOINT].[DATE].jpg”.
- One csv file showing lambdas for all EWAS models, named as: “[PROJECT].[STUDY].lambda.[TIMEPOINT].[DATE].csv”.
- csv files (20 for tier 1 studies, 8 for tier 2 studies) showing the results from DMR analysis (based on the fully adjusted model) for each exposure variable, named as: “[PROJECT].[STUDY].[EXPOSURE].dmr.[TIMEPOINT].[DATE].csv”.

In addition, please also complete the attached Excel file named as “MatVegDiet.[STUDY].cohortinfo.xlsx” and upload it along with other output files. Please note that there are two tabs to fill within the file. This file will ask for general information about your study and analyses. Example answers from ALSPAC are provided in the file.

When you are ready to upload your results, please zip them and email Peiyuan Huang (peiyuan.huang@bristol.ac.uk) and cc Gemma Sharp (g.c.sharp@exeter.ac.uk), and we will provide you with a personal URL for upload.

References

1. Leahy E, Lyons S, Tol R. An Estimate of the Number of Vegetarians in the World. Dublin: The Economic and Social Research Institute (ESRI), 2010.
2. Tan C, Zhao Y, Wang S. Is a vegetarian diet safe to follow during pregnancy? A systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*: Taylor and Francis Inc., 2019:2586-96.
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15. Naeem H, Wong NC, Chatterton Z, et al. Reducing the risk of false discovery enabling identification of biologically significant genome-wide methylation status using the HumanMethylation450 array. *BMC Genomics: BioMed Central Ltd.*, 2014.

Supplementary Note 1. Detailed information about how to derive vegetarian subgroups and plant-based diet indices.

Definition of vegetarian subgroups

A categorical variable for vegetarian subgroups is derived using the definition provided by Jaacks et al.¹ and Yisahak et al.² (except for “semi-vegetarians”). Based on the intake frequency (i.e., times/week) of four food groups – meat (including poultry), fish (including seafood), eggs, and dairy, different subgroups of vegetarians are defined as follows:

- **Vegans:** meat, fish, egg, and dairy intakes together less than once per month (i.e., 0.25 time/week)
- **Lacto-ovo-vegetarians:** meat and fish intakes together less than once per month, and egg and dairy intakes together more than or equal to once per month
- **Pesco-vegetarians:** meat intake less than once per month, and fish intake more than or equal to once per month
- **Non-vegetarians:** no restriction on any food intakes

In this study, vegans and lacto-ovo-vegetarians are combined as “**full vegetarians**”. Please note that we do NOT define “semi-vegetarians” as a vegetarian subgroup because we have found evidence from other cohorts that this group is not stable throughout pregnancy and their dietary pattern should not be considered different from non-vegetarians.

Calculation of plant-based diet indices

The plant-based diet indices (PDIs) were developed by Satija et al.³, including three versions: the overall **PDI**, the healthful PDI (**hPDI**), and the unhealthful PDI (**uPDI**). First, all food items are classified into 18 food groups (including 7 healthy plant food groups, 5 less healthy plant food groups, and 6 animal food groups). Healthy plant food groups include whole grains, fruits, vegetables, nuts, legumes, vegetable oils, and tea/coffee, whereas less healthy plant food groups include fruit juices, sugar-sweetened beverages, refined grains, potatoes, and sweets/desserts; animal food groups include animal fats, dairy, eggs, fish/seafood, meat (poultry and red meat), and miscellaneous animal-based foods (see detailed information about each food group in **Supplementary Table 1**). The intake of food items belonging to each of the 18 food groups is added up, and each food group is divided into quintiles of intake, with each quintile assigned a score between 1 and 5. In the calculation of overall PDI, for each (including healthy and less healthy) plant food group, those with intakes above the highest quintile receive a score of 5, and those with intakes above the second highest quintile but below the highest quintile receive a score of 4, and so on, with a score of 1 for intakes below the lowest quintile (i.e. positive scores). On the other hand, for each animal food group, those with intakes above the highest quintile receive a score of 1, and those with intakes above the second highest quintile but below the highest quintile receive a score of 2, and so on, with a score of 5 for intakes below the lowest quintile (i.e., reverse scores). For hPDI, positive scores are given to healthy plant food groups, and reverse scores to less healthy plant food groups and animal food groups. For uPDI, positive scores are given to less healthy plant food groups, and reverse scores to healthy plant food groups and animal food groups. The 18 food group scores for an individual are summed to obtain the indices, with a range from 18 (the lowest possible score) to 90 (the highest possible score). For example, a higher score of overall PDI indicated greater adherence to a plant-based diet (i.e., higher plant-based and lower animal-based food intakes).

Variable derivation for vegetarian subgroups and plant-based diet indices – using ALSPAC as an example

In ALSPAC, a non-quantitative FFQ⁴ was sent to the women at approximately 32 weeks of gestation, which contained questions asking about the intake frequency (e.g., how many times per week) of 43 food items and some additional questions collecting information on bread, oil, milk, tea, and coffee intakes (see **Supplementary Table 2** for more details about this FFQ). Portion sizes were assumed based on national nutrition survey data⁴. The pregnant women were classified into different vegetarian subgroups according to the definitions above.

As for the calculation of PDIs, ALSPAC data did not have enough granularity to divide the participants into quintiles for some food groups (see **Supplementary Table 3** for the distribution of each food group). Therefore, in this study, we slightly modified the scoring criteria and used tertiles instead of quintiles for the calculation. Positive scores (1-3) or negative scores (3-1) were assigned to each tertile from the lowest to the highest, and the final PDIs ranged from 18 to 54. Where the intake of some food groups had a very skewed distribution, and >33% of participants had zero intakes (e.g., nuts, vegetable oil, sugar-sweetened beverages, and miscellaneous animal-based foods; see **Supplementary Table 3**), we set the first tertile to zero and used the median from the rest of the participants to divide the second and third tertiles. For consistency across studies in this EWAS, we suggest all studies calculate PDIs in a similar way (functions are provided in the R script). Tertile cutoffs for each food group are shown in **Supplementary Table 4**.

Among the 687 complete cases included in the ALSPAC EWAS, there were 19 (2.8%) full vegetarians and 20 (2.9%) pesco-vegetarians (**Supplementary Table 5**). The mean (standard deviation) of PDI, hPDI, and uPDI was 34.59 (3.29), 35.49 (3.39), and 35.44 (3.99), respectively (**Supplementary Table 5**). The distribution of each index did not differ much from a normal distribution (**Supplementary Figure 1**). **Supplementary Table 6** and **Supplementary Figure 2** show the intake of different food groups by vegetarian subgroups and by PDI scores, respectively, and the patterns observed are generally as expected.

References

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Supplementary Table 1. Eighteen food groups and their detailed composition.

Food group	Example food ¹	Item name	Maternal FFQ during pregnancy in ALSPAC			Portion size (g) ²		
			Question ref.	Variable name	Food name ²			
Healthy plant food groups								
Whole grains	Whole grain breakfast cereal, other cooked breakfast cereal, cooked oatmeal, dark bread, brown rice, other grains, bran, wheat germ, popcorn	Brown/granary bread	C7b	c253	Brown bread, average	18		
		Granary bread			Granary bread	18		
		Wholemeal bread	C7c	c254	Wholemeal bread, average	36		
		Rice	C1o	c217	Brown rice, boiled	27		
		Pasta	C1p	c218	Spaghetti, wholemeal, boiled	30		
		Out cereals	C3i	c233	Muesli, Swiss style	17		
					Porridge, made with water	53		
					Ready Brek	10		
		Wholegrain/bran cereals	C3m	c234	All-Bran	10		
					Bran Flakes	8		
					Fruit 'n Fibre	8		
					Weetabix	10		
		Fruits	Raisins or grapes, prunes, bananas, cantaloupe, watermelon, fresh apples or pears, oranges, grapefruit, strawberries, blueberries, peaches or apricots or plums	Crispbreads	C3p	c237	Crispbread, rye	20
Fresh fruit	C3h			c229	Apples, eating, average, raw	17		
					Bananas	17		
					Grapes, average	17		
					Oranges	21		
					Peaches, raw	18		
					Pears, average, raw	28		
					Brussels sprouts, boiled in unsalted water	36		
					Cabbage, boiled in unsalted water, average	38		
					Spring greens, boiled in unsalted water	19		
Vegetables	Tomatoes, tomato juice, tomato sauce, broccoli, cabbage, cauliflower, Brussels sprouts, carrots, mixed vegetables, yellow or winter squash, eggplant or zucchini, yams or sweet potatoes, spinach cooked, spinach raw, kale or mustard or chard greens, iceberg or head lettuce, romaine or leaf lettuce, celery, mushrooms, beets, alfalfa sprouts, garlic, corn	Green leafy vegetables	C3c	c224	Brussels sprouts, boiled in unsalted water	36		
					Cabbage, boiled in unsalted water, average	38		
					Spring greens, boiled in unsalted water	19		
		Other green vegetables	C3d	c225	Green beans/French beans, boiled in unsalted water	23		
					Broccoli, green, boiled in unsalted water	21		
					Cauliflower, boiled in unsalted water	23		
					Leeks, boiled in unsalted water	19		
		Carrots	C3e	c226	Carrots, old, boiled in unsalted water	60		
		Other root vegetables	C3f	c227	Parsnip, boiled in unsalted water	26		
					Sweet potato, boiled in unsalted water	24		
					Turip, boiled in unsalted water	12		
		Salad	C3g	c228	Cucumber, raw	23		
					Lettuce, average, raw	30		
					Tomatoes, raw	60		
		Nuts	Nuts, peanut butter	Sweetcorn	C3b	c223	Sweetcorn, kernels, canned, re-heated, drained	21
Tomatoes	C3i			c230	Tomatoes, canned, whole contents	80		
Nuts	C3t			c241	Almonds	8		
					Brazil nuts	8		
					Hazelnuts	8		
					Peanuts, roasted and salted	28		
Tahini	C3v			c243	Hummus	10		
					Tahini paste	10		
Legumes	Siring beans, tofu or soybeans, beans or lentils, peas or lima beans			Baked beans	C3a	c222	Baked beans, canned in tomato sauce, re-heated	135
				Legumes	C3b	c223	Peas, frozen, boiled in unsalted water	35
					Peas, canned, re-heated, drained	18		
		Pulses	C3s	c240	Chick peas, whole, dried, boiled in unsalted water	40		
					Lentils, red, split, dried, boiled in unsalted water	40		
					Red kidney beans, canned, re-heated, drained	40		
		Bean curd	C3u	c242	Tofu, soya bean, steamed, fried	80		
		Meat replacement	C3w	c244	Vegebanger mix, made up with water, fried in vegetable oil	37		
Vegetable oils ³	Oil-based salad dressing, vegetable oil used for cooking	Soya milk	C10g	c282	Soya milk, plain	100		
		Sunflower/soya/corn/olive oil	C8e	c270	Corn oil	30		
					Olive oil	100		
					Soya oil	30		
					Sunflower oil	30		
		Other vegetable oil	C8f	c272	Vegetable oil, blended, average	100		
		Tea and coffee	Tea, coffee, decaffeinated coffee	Regular tea	C12a	c300	Regular tea	225
				Decaffeinated tea	C12e	c303	Decaffeinated tea	225
				Regular coffee	C12d	c305	Regular coffee	225
				Decaffeinated coffee	C12f	c308	Decaffeinated coffee	225
Herbal tea	C14b			c316	Herbal tea	225		
Less healthy plant food groups								
Fruit juices	Apple cider (non-alcoholic) or juice, orange juice, grapefruit juice, other fruit juice	Fruit juice (tinned)	C3j	c230	Orange juice, unsweetened	80		
		Fruit juice (not tinned)	C3j	c231	Apple juice, unsweetened	32		
Refined grains	Refined grain breakfast cereal, white bread, English muffins or bagels or rolls, muffins or biscuits, white rice, pancakes or waffles, crackers, pasta	White bread	C7a	c252	Orange juice, unsweetened	96		
		Chapatis/naan bread	C7d	c255	Pineapple juice, unsweetened	32		
					White bread, sliced	36		
					Chapatis, made without fat	28		
					Naan bread	40		
		Rice	C1o	c217	White rice, easy cook, boiled	108		
		Pasta	C1p	c218	Spaghetti, white, boiled	120		
		Other cereals	C3n	c235	Corn Flakes	6		
					Frosties	6		
					Rice Krispies	6		
Potatoes	French fries, baked or mashed potatoes, potato or corn chips	Crisps	C1q	c219	Shreddies	9		
		Soft drinks	C4	c247	Special K	6		
					Chips, retail, fried in blended oil	42		
					Chips, straight cut, frozen, fried in blended oil	33		
					Chips, French fries, retail	23		
					Oven chips, frozen, baked	33		
					Chips, homemade, fried in blended oil	33		
		Roast potatoes	C1m	c215	Old potatoes, roast in blended oil	103		
		Potatoes (other)	C1n	c216	New potatoes, boiled in unsalted water	20		
					Old potatoes, baked, flesh and skin	30		
			Old potatoes, baked, flesh only	27				
			Old potatoes, boiled in unsalted water	60				
Sugar sweetened beverages	Colas with caffeine & sugar, colas without caffeine but with sugar, other carbonated beverages with sugar, non-carbonated fruit drinks with sugar	Potato crisps	C4	c247	Potato crisps	27		
		Soft drinks	C4	c247	Cola	110		
Sweets and desserts	Chocolates, candy bars, candy without chocolate, cookies (home-baked & ready-made), brownies, doughnuts, cake (home-baked & ready-made), sweet roll (home-baked & ready-made), pie (home-baked & ready-made), jams or jellies or preserves or syrup or honey	Cola			Fruit juice drink, carbonated, ready to drink	110		
					Lemonade	110		
		Pudding	C3k	c232	Gateau	14		
					Crumble, fruit	28		
					Fruit pie, pastry top and bottom	18		
					Sponge pudding	18		
					Cheesecake, frozen	20		
					Rice pudding, canned	25		
		Cakes	C3o	c236	Fancy iced cakes, individual	6		
					Fruit cake, rich	14		
					Sponge cake, jam filled	12		
					Doughnuts, jam	15		
					Eccles cake	9		
		Biscuits	C3q	c238	Digestive biscuits, plain	3		
					Semi-sweet biscuits	2		
					Short-sweet biscuits	3		
					Kit Kat	6		
		Chocolate bars	C3r	c239	Mars bar	33		
			Twix	28				
Chocolate	C3x	c245	Chocolate, fancy and filled	10				
			Chocolate, milk	30				
			Chocolate, plain	10				
Sweets	C3y	c246	Chew sweets	6				
			Fruit pastilles	7				
			Fudge	5				
			Liquorice allsorts	9				
			Peppermints	5				
			Toffees, mixed	8				
Animal food groups								
Animal fat ⁴	Butter added to food, butter or lard used for cooking	Butter, ghee, dripping lard, solid cooking fat	C8a (on bread)	c260	Butter	100		
			C8a (for cooking)	c261	Compound cooking fat	10		
					Dripping, beef	10		

					Ghee, butter	5	
					Ghee, palm	5	
					Lard	35	
					Butter	35	
Dairy	Skim low fat milk, whole milk, cream, sour cream, sherbet, ice cream, yogurt, cottage or ricotta cheese, cream cheese, other cheese	Whole milk	C10a	c276	Whole milk, pasteurised	100	
		Semi-skimmed milk	C10b	c277	Semi-skimmed milk, pasteurized	100	
		Skimmed milk	C10c	c278	Skimmed milk, pasteurized	100	
		Sterilised milk	C10d	c279	Whole milk, sterilised	100	
		Goat/sheep milk	C10f	c281	Goat milk, pasteurised	50	
						Sheep milk, raw	50
		Cheese	C1j	c209	Cheddar, average	23	
Egg	Eggs	Eggs/quiche	C1i	c208	Edam	23	
						Eggs, chicken, boiled	17
						Omelette, plain	40
Fish and seafood	Canned tuna, dark meat fish, other fish, shrimp or lobster or scallops	White fish	C1f	c205	Quiche, cheese and egg	47	
					Cod, baked, filets	30	
					Haddock, coated in crumbs, fried in blended oil	30	
		Oily fish	C1g	c206	Plaice, in butter, fried in blended oil	50	
					Fish fingers, grilled	20	
					Herring, grilled	20	
					Kipper, baked	22	
					Mackerel, fried	27	
					Pilchards, canned in tomato sauce	18	
		Shellfish	C1h	c207	Salmon, canned	17	
					Tuna, canned in brine, drained	15	
					Crab, canned in brine, drained	21	
					Prawns, boiled	15	
					Scampi, in breadcrumbs, frozen, fried	43	
					Mussels, boiled	10	
Meat	Chicken or turkey with skin, chicken or turkey without skin, bacon, hot dogs, processed meats, liver, hamburger, beef or pork or lamb mixed dish, beef or pork or lamb main dish	Processed meat	C1a	c200	Beefburgers, chilled/frozen, fried	40	
		Meat pies	C1b	c201	Pork sausages, chilled, grilled	40	
		Red meat	C1c	c202	Cornish pastie	39	
					Pork pie, individual	35	
					Sausage rolls, flaky pastry, homemade	15	
					Steak and kidney/Beef pie, individual, chilled/frozen, baked	40	
					Beef, topside, roasted well-done, lean and fat	23	
		Poultry	C1d	c203	Lamb, shoulder, whole, roasted, lean and fat	23	
					Pork, loin chops, grilled, lean and fat	30	
		Organ meat	C1e	c204	Bacon rashers, middle, grilled, lean and fat	12	
					Chicken, roast, meat and skin	100	
					Heart, ox, stewed	25	
Miscellaneous animal-based foods	Pizza, chowder or cream soup, mayonnaise or other creamy salad dressing	Pizza	C1k	c210	Kidney, pig, stewed	28	
					Liver, lamb, fried	25	
					Pate, liver	20	
					Pizza, cheese and tomato	115	
					Pizza, cheese and tomato, retail, frozen	115	

¹ Provided by Satija et al. (2016) for developing the plant-based diet indices, based on the FFQ data from the Nurses' Health Study, the Nurses' Health Study 2, and the Health Professionals Follow-Up Study in the United States (DOI:10.1371/journal.pmed.1002039).

² Assumed by Rogers & Emmett (1998) based on the data from the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food in 1991 (DOI: 10.1038/sj.ejn.1600543); the assumed portion sizes were used for deriving the plant-based diet indices in the present study.

³ Margarine was excluded from the plant-based diet indices by Satija et al. (2016) due to its changing fatty acid composition over time; in the present study, we also excluded hard or soft margarine, polyunsaturated margarine, and low fat spread from the indices as it was not clear whether FFQ, food frequency questionnaire; ALSPAC, Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children.

Supplementary Table 2. Maternal FFQ administered at 32 weeks gestation in ALSPAC.

Question ref.	Variable name	Question	Answer options
C1		We are interested in your diet. How many times nowadays do you eat:	Never or rarely / Once in 2 weeks / 1-3 times a week / 4-7 time a week / More than once a day
a	c200	Sausages, Burgers	
b	c201	Pies, Pasties (pork pie, steak/meat pie etc.)	
c	c202	Meat (beef, lamb, pork, ham, bacon etc.)	
d	c203	Poultry (chicken, turkey etc)	
e	c204	Liver, liver pate, kidney, heart	
f	c205	White fish (cod, haddock, plaice, fish fingers etc)	
g	c206	Other fish sh (pilchards, sardines, mackerel, tuna, herring, kippers, trout, salmon etc)	
h	c207	Shellfish (prawns, crab, cockles, mussels etc)	
i	c208	Eggs, quiche	
j	c209	Cheese	
k	c210	Pizza	
l	c211	Chips	
m	c215	Roast potatoes (cooked in fat)	
n	c216	Boiled, mashed, jacket potatoes	
o	c217	Rice (boiled)	
p	c218	Pasta (eg. spaghetti, Pot Noodles, lasagna)	
q	c219	Crisps	
r	c220	Fried foods (eg. fried fish, eggs, bacon, chops etc)	
C3		How many times a week nowadays do you eat:	Never or rarely / Once in 2 weeks / 1-3 times a week / 4-7 time a week / More than once a day
a	c222	Baked beans	
b	c223	Peas, sweetcorn, broad beans	
c	c224	Cabbage, brussel sprouts, kale and other green leafy vegetables	
d	c225	Other green vegetables (cauliflower, runner beans, leeks etc)	
e	c226	Carrots	
f	c227	Other root vegetables (turnip,swede,parsnip etc)	
g	c228	Salad (lettuce, tomato, cucumber etc)	
h	c229	Fresh fruit (apple, pear, banana, orange, bunch of grapes etc)	
i	c230	Tinned juice (including tomato juice)	
j	c231	Pure juice not in tin	
k	c232	Pudding (eg fruit pie, crumble, cheesecake, milk pudding, mousse, gateaux)	
l	c233	Oat cereals (eg porridge, Ready Brek, muesli)	
m	c234	Wholegrain or bran cereals (eg. All Bran, Bran Flakes, Weetabix, Wheatflakes, Fruit & Fibre)	
n	c235	Other cereals (eg Corn- flakes, Rice Krispies, Special K, Frosties)	
o	c236	Cakes or buns (fruit cake, sponge, teacake, buns, doughnut, flapjack, scone, custard tart,cream cake etc)	
p	c237	Crispbreads (Ryvita, crackerbread etc)	
q	c238	Biscuits (digestive, shortcake, Hob Nobs, Rich Tea, Nice, Marie, chocolate biscuits,Penguin Club, Kit Kat etc)	
r	c239	Chocolate bars (Mars, Twix, Wispa, Bounty,Creme Egg etc)	
s	c240	Pulses - dried peas, beans, lentils, chick peas	
t	c241	Nuts, nut roast	
u	c242	Bean Curd (eg. Tofu, miso)	
v	c243	Tahini	
w	c244	Soya 'Meat', T.V.P., Vegeburgers	
x	c245	Chocolate (dairy milk or plain, nut, fruit filled etc)	
y	c246	Sweets (peppermints, boiled sweets, toffees etc)	
C4		When you have a soft drink, how often do you choose low calorie or diet drinks?	Always / Sometimes / Not at all / Don't drink soft drinks
	c247	Frequency of choosing diet soft drink	
C5		How many pieces of bread, rolls or chappatis do you eat on a usual day?	Less than 1 / 1-2 / 3-4 / 5 or more
	c250	Slices of bread eaten per day	
C7		What types of bread do you eat most days?	Yes / No
a	c252	White bread	
b	c253	brown/granary bread	
c	c254	Wholemeal bread	
d	c255	Chappatis, nan bread	
e	c256	Don't usually eat any bread	
C8		What sort of fat do you mainly use: (i) On bread or vegetables (ii) For frying	Yes / No
a		Butter, Ghee, Dripping Lard, solid cooking fat	
	c260	Mainly use butter etc on bread or vegetables	
	c261	Mainly use butter etc for frying	
b		Hard or soft margarine e.g. Blue Band, Stork, supermarket own brand	
	c263	Mainly use hard or soft margarine on bread or vegetables	
	c264	Mainly use hard or soft margarine for frying	
c		Polyunsaturated margarine e.g. Flora, sunflower, Vitalite	
	c265	Mainly use polyunsaturated margarine on bread or vegetables	
	c266	Mainly use polyunsaturated margarine for frying	
d		Low fat spread e.g. Outline, Delight, St.Ivel Gold	
	c267	Mainly use low fat spread on bread or vegetables	
	c268	Mainly use low fat spread for frying	
e		Sunflower, soya, corn, olive oil	
	c269	Mainly use sunflower oil or similar on vegetables	
	c270	Mainly fry with sunflower oil or similar	
f		Other vegetable oil	
	c271	Mainly use other vegetable oil on bread or vegetables	
	c272	Mainly use other vegetable oil for frying	
g		Other (please describe)	
	c273	Other fat used mainly on bread or vegetables	
	c274	Other fat used mainly for frying	
C9		How many slices of bread (or rolls) spread with fat do you eat each day? (include bought sandwiches)	Number of slices
	c275	Slices of bread with fat daily	
C10		What type(s) of milk do you use?	Yes usually / Yes sometimes / No not at all
a	c276	Full fat (silver or gold top)	
b	c277	Semi Skimmed (red stripe)	
c	c278	Skimmed (blue stripe)	
d	c279	Sterilised	
f	c281	Goat/sheep milk	
g	c282	Soya milk	
h	c283	Other (please describe)	
C12			
a	c300	How many cups of tea do you drink in a day? (do not include herbal teas)	Number of cups
c	c303	How many of the cups of tea you drink each day are decaffeinated?	Number of cups
d	c305	How many cups of coffee do you drink in a day?	Number of cups
f	c308	How many of the cups of the coffee you drink each day are decaffeinated?	Number of cups
C13			
a	c310	How many drinks of cola do you have in a week?	Number of drinks
b	c312	How many cans of cola that you drink each week are decaffeinated?	Number of cans
C14			
b	c316	How many cups/mugs of herbal teas have you drunk in the past week?	Number of cups/mugs

FFQ, food frequency questionnaire; ALSPAC, Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children.

Supplementary Table 3. Distribution of the intake of the eighteen food groups in ALSPAC pregnant women included in the EWAS analysis.

	N	Percentile of intake														
		Min	P10	P20	P25	P30	P33.3	P40	P50	P60	P66.7	P70	P75	P80	P90	Max
Whole grains (g/day)	687	0.00	16.29	44.14	55.36	66.84	70.44	81.57	100.00	124.00	140.36	146.01	155.32	164.69	204.24	305.43
Fruits (g/day)	687	0.00	33.71	33.71	92.71	92.71	92.71	92.71	92.71	92.71	168.57	168.57	168.57	168.57	168.57	168.57
Vegetables (g/day)	687	0.00	60.94	80.00	86.79	93.71	99.95	106.57	119.79	129.77	141.00	149.67	163.07	168.41	215.67	446.29
Nuts (g/day)	687	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.71	3.71	3.71	3.71	14.86	40.86
Legumes (g/day)	687	0.00	13.43	23.93	24.79	24.79	31.79	42.36	53.71	53.71	53.71	53.71	62.29	76.50	90.61	359.14
Vegetable oils (g/day)	687	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.97	11.11	12.73	13.64	14.73	44.44	206.25
Tea and coffee (g/day)	687	0.00	450.00	675.00	675.00	900.00	900.00	900.00	1125.00	1125.00	1350.00	1350.00	1350.00	1414.29	1800.00	4500.00
Fruit juices (g/day)	687	0.00	0.00	11.43	17.14	45.71	45.71	45.71	68.57	125.71	125.71	125.71	125.71	131.43	228.57	342.86
Refined grains (g/day)	687	0.00	18.64	41.83	43.29	51.94	62.45	65.14	67.50	74.57	88.93	91.07	95.36	109.07	140.61	326.40
Potatoes (g/day)	687	0.00	41.07	58.21	60.14	65.93	80.29	88.00	107.64	119.36	123.14	127.07	136.64	144.79	170.00	267.86
Sugar sweetened beverages (g/day)	687	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	23.57	47.14	1178.57
Sweets and desserts (g/day)	687	0.00	17.14	33.24	36.71	43.14	45.44	52.64	63.36	77.29	86.86	91.07	98.29	111.54	155.21	279.50
Animal fat (g/day)	687	0.00	28.57	40.00	49.29	57.14	57.14	57.14	66.67	72.22	85.71	85.71	97.14	114.29	125.79	255.56
Dairy (g/day)	687	0.00	113.14	113.14	113.14	136.14	136.14	136.14	136.14	213.14	213.14	213.14	213.14	236.14	236.14	413.14
Egg (g/day)	687	0.00	0.00	7.43	7.43	7.43	7.43	7.43	29.71	29.71	29.71	29.71	29.71	29.71	29.71	81.71
Fish and seafood (g/day)	687	0.00	0.00	9.29	15.64	17.79	17.79	17.79	37.14	43.29	45.64	45.64	49.64	71.14	71.14	265.57
Meat (g/day)	687	0.00	13.43	38.00	47.21	53.71	53.71	59.43	64.36	68.64	85.50	91.21	97.71	103.43	113.43	328.29
Miscellaneous animal-based foods (g/day)	687	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	16.43	16.43	16.43	16.43	16.43	16.43	16.43	65.71	180.71

ALSPAC, Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children. EWAS, epigenome-wide association study.

Supplementary Table 4. Tertile cutoffs of the intake of the eighteen food groups in ALSPAC

	Cut-off	N		
		T1	T2	T3
Whole grains (g/day)	T1: 0-70.29 T2: 70.64-140.29 T3: 140.36-305.43	229	228	230
Fruits (g/day)	T1: 0-33.71 T2: 92.71-92.71 T3: 168.57-168.57	147	279	261
Vegetables (g/day)	T1: 0-99.86 T2: 100.07-140.93 T3: 141-446.29	229	227	231
Nuts (g/day)	T1: 0-0 T2: 1.43-3.71 T3: 5.14-40.86	444	153	90
Legumes (g/day)	T1: 0-30.57 T2: 33.36-53.43 T3: 53.71-359.14	229	87	371
Vegetable oils (g/day)	T1: 0-0 T2: 5.56-13.64 T3: 15-206.25	388	161	138
Tea and coffee (g/day)	T1: 0-803.25 T2: 900-1318.5 T3: 1350-4500	187	262	238
Fruit juices (g/day)	T1: 0-34.29 T2: 45.71-114.29 T3: 125.71-342.86	196	161	330
Refined grains (g/day)	T1: 0-62.36 T2: 62.57-88.71 T3: 88.93-326.4	229	226	232
Potatoes (g/day)	T1: 0-79.43 T2: 80.29-122.71 T3: 123.14-267.86	227	207	253
Sugar sweetened beverages (g/day)	T1: 0-0 T2: 23.57-47.14 T3: 70.71-1178.57	540	82	65
Sweets and desserts (g/day)	T1: 0-45.29 T2: 45.64-86.71 T3: 86.86-279.5	229	227	231
Animal fat (g/day)	T1: 0-56.67 T2: 57.14-84.09 T3: 85.71-255.56	205	243	239
Dairy (g/day)	T1: 0-113.14 T2: 136.14-203.29 T3: 213.14-413.14	190	208	289
Egg (g/day)	T1: 0-0 T2: 7.43-7.43 T3: 29.71-81.71	89	220	378
Fish and seafood (g/day)	T1: 0-15.64 T2: 17.79-43.5 T3: 45.64-265.57	177	257	253
Meat (g/day)	T1: 0-49.79 T2: 53.71-84.86 T3: 85.5-328.29	181	275	231
Miscellaneous animal-based foods (g/day)	T1: 0-0 T2: 16.43-16.43 T3: 65.71-180.71	273	321	93

T1, the first tertile; T2, the second tertile; T3: the third tertile.

ALSPAC, Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children. EWAS, epigenome-wide association study.

Supplementary Table 5. Descriptive statistics for vegetarian subgroups

	Total N	N (%) or mean (SD)
Vegetarian subgroups	687	
Non-vegetarian		648 (94.3%)
Pesco-vegetarian		20 (2.9%)
Full vegetarian ¹		19 (2.8%)
Overall plant-based diet index (PDI)	687	34.59 (3.29)
Healthful plant-based diet index (hPDI)	687	35.49 (3.39)
Unhealthful plant-based diet index (uPDI)	687	35.44 (3.99)

¹Including 19 lacto-ovo-vegetarians and 0 vegans.

ALSPAC, Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children. EWAS, epigenome-wide association study.

Supplementary Figure 1. Distribution of the overall plant-based diet index (left), healthful plant-based diet index (middle), and unhealthful plant-based diet index (right). PDI, overall plant-based diet index. hPDI, healthful plant-based diet index. uPDI, unhealthful plant-based diet index. ALSPAC, Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children. EWAS, ep

Supplementary Table 6. Intakes of the 18 food groups and plant-based diet indices by vegetaria

	Vegetarian subgroups			
	Non-vegetarian (N = 648)	Pesco-vegetarian (N = 20)	Full vegetarian	
			Lacto-ovo-vegetarian (N = 19)	Vegan (N = 0)
Whole grains (g/day)	105.58 (68.44)	156.02 (58.04)	139.55 (56.58)	NA
Fruits (g/day)	105.75 (53.81)	142.86 (42.14)	134.41 (48.86)	NA
Vegetables (g/day)	127.08 (61.40)	189.18 (99.83)	144.53 (77.38)	NA
Nuts (g/day)	2.51 (5.48)	10.66 (10.52)	9.85 (9.72)	NA
Legumes (g/day)	48.85 (34.16)	101.05 (48.13)	103.92 (58.26)	NA
Vegetable oils (g/day)	11.32 (20.71)	9.26 (17.70)	10.72 (18.43)	NA
Tea and coffee (g/day)	1094.00 (537.02)	1007.68 (509.53)	962.59 (514.00)	NA
Fruit juices (g/day)	91.56 (79.95)	139.43 (98.41)	107.97 (51.00)	NA
Refined grains (g/day)	76.84 (47.61)	75.87 (41.76)	93.23 (46.75)	NA
Potatoes (g/day)	105.87 (49.38)	82.49 (46.40)	91.34 (50.57)	NA
Sugar sweetened beverages (g/day)	20.59 (69.86)	16.50 (53.04)	13.65 (28.67)	NA
Sweets and desserts (g/day)	76.57 (53.92)	65.26 (46.95)	55.29 (31.55)	NA
Animal fat (g/day)	72.89 (40.07)	82.20 (45.64)	78.96 (39.23)	NA
Dairy (g/day)	172.63 (65.12)	181.47 (68.70)	178.40 (65.53)	NA
Egg (g/day)	20.43 (17.66)	36.40 (24.92)	29.71 (15.06)	NA
Fish and seafood (g/day)	36.76 (28.64)	51.64 (33.86)	0.00 (0.00)	NA
Meat (g/day)	74.14 (37.12)	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)	NA
Miscellaneous animal-based foods (g/day)	16.43 (20.75)	19.71 (40.80)	24.21 (26.47)	NA
Overall plant-based diet index (PDI)	34.38 (3.20)	37.25 (2.86)	38.79 (2.74)	NA
Healthful plant-based diet index (hPDI)	35.29 (3.32)	38.55 (3.25)	38.89 (2.66)	NA
Unhealthful plant-based diet index (uPDI)	35.54 (3.99)	32.65 (3.39)	35.00 (3.37)	NA

Data presented as mean (standard deviation).

ALSPAC, Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children. EWAS, epigenome-wide association study.

Supplementary Figure 2. Correlation matrix between plant-based diet indices and intakes of the 18 food groups in ALSPAC pregnant women included in the EWAS PDI, overall plant-based diet index. hPDI, healthful plant-based diet index. uPDI, unhealthful plant-based diet index. ALSPAC, Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children. EWAS, ep

COHORT INFORMATION for the Maternal Vegetarian Diet (MatVegDiet) PACE EWAS Project	Example answer from ALSPAC	[YOUR STUDY]
GENERAL INFORMATION		
Study name	Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (ALSPAC)	
Study design	Prospective birth cohort study	
Analyst name	Peiyuan Huang	
Analyst contact	peiyuan.huang@bristol.ac.uk	
Analysis date (YYYYMMDD)	20221130	
EXPOSURES OF INTEREST		
Tier 1 (with data on all 18 food groups) or Tier 2 (with data on meat, fish/seafood, egg, and dairy intakes only)?	Tier 1	
How was maternal dietary intake assessed (e.g., FFQ, 24HR, or food diary)?	FFQ	
About your dietary assessment tool: which reference period (e.g., 1 month or 3 months) for FFQ or how many days registered for 24HR?	Not clearly specified	
When was the dietary assessment administered (e.g., at which week of gestation or in which trimester of pregnancy)?	At ~32 weeks of gestation	
Has your dietary assessment tool been validated before? If so, please specify which method was used (e.g., biomarkers, 24HR, or food diary) and provide the link of the validation study.	No	
Was your dietary assessment tool designed for a specific trait? If so, which trait?	No	
In which unit was maternal dietary intake measured (e.g., in g/day or times/day)?	g/day	
Availability and details of each food group	To answer this question, please fill in the table in the next tab "Food group check"	
When calculating tertiles and PDIs in your data, did you need further adaption of the codes provided? If so, please describe any changes you made.	Yes. In some food groups, >33% of participants had zero intake. In these cases, we set the first tertile to zero and use the median of the rest to divide the second and third tertiles (this has already been incorporated into the current version of codes).	
COVARIATES		
How did you define the following variables?		
Maternal education		
Level 0	Below A-levels	
Level 1	A-levels and above	
Maternal smoking status		
Level 0	No smoking or quit in the first trimester	
Level 1	Sustained smoking during pregnancy	
Maternal BMI		
When was maternal weight measured (e.g., pre-pregnancy or at early stage of pregnancy)?	Pre-pregnancy	
Maternal dietary supplementation		
Level 0	No supplement use by 18 weeks gestation	
Level 1	At least one of the following supplements used by 18 weeks gestation: iron, zinc, calcium, folic acid, multivitamins, or "other"	
Ethnicity		
What ethnicity are the individuals in your study? If there are multiple ethnicities, please provide the sample size of each ethnicity.	White European	
Other covariates		
Did you include any extra covariates, other than those specified in the analysis plan? If so, please provide details and reasons.	No	
Did you remove any covariates specified in the analysis plan? If so, please provide details and reasons.	No	
METHYLATION DATA		
Which measurement method did you use (e.g., EPIC or 450K)?	450K	
Which time point of methylation data and samples (e.g., cord blood or neonatal blood) did you use?	Birth, cord blood	
Which method did you use to normalise methylation data?	Functional normalisation using the meffil R package	
Which QC steps did you use?	Removed probes with high detection p-values, probes on sex chromosomes, and control probes	
Were methylation data untransformed Illumina beta-values on a scale of 0 to 1?	Yes	
Did you remove outliers using the IQR*3 (Tukey) method?	Yes	
SCRIPT AND CODES		
Did any of the codes/functions provided not work (e.g., PDI calculation, SVA, EWAS, DMIR, etc)? If so, please provide details and specify any changes you made.	No	
OTHER INFORMATION		
Any additional information worth noting?	No	

Food group	Example answer from ALSPAC		[YOUR STUDY]	
	Available?	Food items contained	Available?	Food items contained
Whole grains	Yes	Brown/granary bread, wholemeal bread, brown rice, wholemeal pasta, oat cereals, wholegrain/bran cereals, crispbreads		
Fruits	Yes	Apples, bananas, grapes, oranges, peaches, pears		
Vegetables	Yes	Green leafy vegetables, other green vegetables, carrots, other root vegetables, salad		
Nuts	Yes	Nuts, tahini		
Legumes	Yes	Baked beans, legumes, pulses, bean curd, meat replacement, soya milk		
Vegetable oils	Yes	Sunflower oil, soya oil, corn oil, olive oil, vegetable oil		
Tea and coffee	Yes	Regular tea, decaffeinated tea, regular coffee, decaffeinated coffee, herbal tea		
Fruit juices	Yes	Apple juice, orange juice, pineapple juice, tomato juice		
Refined grains	Yes	White bread, chapatis/naan bread, white rice, white pasta, other cereals (e.g., corn flakes)		
Potatoes	Yes	Chips, roast potatoes, potatoes (other), crisps		
Sugar-sweetened beverages	Yes	Cola, carbonated fruit juice drink, lemonade		
Sweets and desserts	Yes	Pudding, cake, biscuits, chocolate bars, chocolate, sweets		
Animal fat	Yes	Butter, ghee, dripping lard, solid cooking fat		
Dairy	Yes	Whole milk, semi-skimmed milk, skimmed milk, sterilised milk, goat/sheep milk, cheese		
Egg	Yes	Eggs, omelette, quiche		
Fish and seafood	Yes	White fish, oily fish, shellfish		
Meat	Yes	Processed meat, meat pies, red meat, poultry, organ meat		
Miscellaneous animal-based foods	Yes	Pizza		

```
#####
# MATERNAL VEGETARIAN/PLANT-BASED DIET AND CORD BLOOD DNA METHYLATION #
# EWAS Analysis Plan Code #
#-----#
# Peiyuan (Ran) Huang #
# August 2024 #
# Acknowledgements: Gemma Sharp, Leanne Kupers, Giulia Mancano #
#####

#####

# The following R code will allow you to complete all the EWAS requested in the vegetarian diet EWAS analysis plan.
# The code also produces .csv files summarising the variables included in the EWASes.
# [NOTE: You should not have to rewrite or add to the following code,
# UNLESS otherwise stated (see the "[PLEASE CHANGE]" notice).]
#
# There are two input files required for this analysis:
#
# 1. pheno: A dataframe containing all the phenotype data needed for this project.
# Each row is a sample (individual) and each column is a different variable.
# Necessary variable names are:
# - Sample ID (1): "sample.id"
# - Food groups (18): "wholegrain", "fruit", "vegetable", "nut", "legume", "vegetableoil", "teacoffee", "fruitjuice", "refinedgrain", "potato", "sugarbeverage",
"sweetdessert", "animalfat", "dairy", "egg", "fishseafood", "meat", "misc.animal"
# - Intake frequency of key food groups (4): "meat_freq", "fishseafood_freq", "egg_freq", "dairy_freq"
# - Covariates (8): "sex", "mat.age", "mat.edu", "mat.parity", "mat.smoking", "mat.bmi", "mat.suppl", "mat.kcal"
# - Cell types (7): "CD8T", "CD4T", "NK", "Bcell", "Mono", "Gran", "nRBC"
# Please use this exact order of variable names and do not include other columns in the pheno file.
# Please use the Salas reference set for cell type correction
# If these columns are named differently in your dataset, please rename the columns accordingly
# Details on how to code these variables are provided in the analysis plan and supplementary documents.
#
# 2. meth: A matrix of methylation Illumina beta values. Each column is a sample and each row is a probe on the array (450k or EPIC).
# Column names must correspond to the sample.id column in pheno.
#
# If you have any questions about this script, please contact Peiyuan (Ran) Huang (peiyuan.huang@bristol.ac.uk) and cc Dr Gemma Sharp
(g.c.sharp@exeter.ac.uk).

# Update on 2023/08/08: No longer consider semi-vegetarian as a vegetarian subgroup (see changes in Lines 228-250)

#####

#-----#
# Packages & Functions #----#
#-----#

# Load required packages
# [NOTE: If these are not already installed, you will have to install them as the first step.]
library(tableone)
library(matrixStats)
library(limma)
library(data.table)
library(plyr)
library(sva)
library(qqman)
library(dmrff)

# Setup the necessary functions

## Function to remove outliers using the Tukey IQR*3 method
IQR.removal <- function(meth) {
  rowIQR <- rowIQRs(meth, na.rm = T)
  row2575 <- rowQuantiles(meth, probs = c(0.25, 0.75), na.rm = T)
  maskL <- meth < row2575[, 1] - 3 * rowIQR
  maskU <- meth > row2575[, 2] + 3 * rowIQR
  meth[maskL] <- NA
  meth[maskU] <- NA
  return(meth)
}

## Function to run EWAS
## [NOTE: Here we use least squares instead of robust regression lmFit, as we will manually remove outliers before running EWAS.]
ewas.function <- function(meth, pheno, variable.of.interest) {
  model.covariates <- colnames(pheno)[-which(colnames(pheno) %in% c(variable.of.interest, "sample.id"))]
  des <- model.matrix(reformulate(paste0("pheno$", c(variable.of.interest, model.covariates))))
  fit <- lmFit(meth, des, method = "ls") # Use least squares instead of robust regression (method = "robust")
  fit.ebayes <- eBayes(fit)
  n <- rowSums(!is.na(meth))
  se <- sqrt(fit.ebayes$s2.post) * fit.ebayes$stdev.unscaled[, grep(paste0(variable.of.interest, collapse = "|"), colnames(fit.ebayes$stdev.unscaled))]
  res <- data.frame(n = n,
    coef = fit.ebayes$coefficients[, grep(paste0(variable.of.interest, collapse = "|"), colnames(fit.ebayes$coefficients))],
    se = se,
    p = fit.ebayes$p.value[, grep(paste0(variable.of.interest, collapse = "|"), colnames(fit.ebayes$p.value))])
}
```

```

return(res)
}

#-----#
#           Load & Prepare Phenotype Data           #----
#-----#

# [PLEASE CHANGE] Set to your working directory where you want to save the results from this script
setwd("...")

# Set initial parameters
# [NOTE: We will use 20 surrogate variables (SVs; named as sv1-sv20) to adjust for batch in this study.
#   See details in the "Generate Surrogate Variables" section below.]
study <- "ALSPAC" # [PLEASE CHANGE] Set your study identifier
analysis.date <- format(Sys.Date(), "%Y%m%d") # Automatically set to the date on which you perform the analyses
timepoint <- "birth" # Should be "birth" for this study
cell.names <- c("CD8T", "CD4T", "NK", "Bcell", "Mono", "Gran", "nRBC") # Should be these 7 cell types of according to the Salas reference
traits.and.covariates <- c(
  ## 5 exposure variables of interest
  "veggie1", "veggie2", "PDI", "hPDI", "uPDI",

  ## 18 food groups
  "wholegrain", "fruit", "vegetable", "nut", "legume", "vegetableoil", "teacoffee", "fruitjuice", "refinedgrain", "potato", "sugarbeverage", "sweetdessert",
  "animalfat", "dairy", "egg", "fishseafood", "meat", "misc.animal",

  ## Covariates (including SVs)
  "sex", "mat.age", "mat.edu", "mat.parity", "mat.smoking", "mat.bmi", "mat.kcal", "mat.suppl", paste0("sv", 1:20)
) # You can also add selection factors relevant to your cohort

# Set up 4 models for each of the 5 exposure variables
# [NOTE: The 5 exposure variables include:
#   - "veggie1": Full vegetarian vs. non-vegetarian
#   - "veggie2": Full vegetarian + pesco-vegetarian vs. non-vegetarian
#   - PDI: The overall plant-based diet index
#   - hPDI: The healthful plant-based diet index
#   - uPDI: The unhealthful plant-based diet index]
for (my_exp in c("veggie1", "veggie2", "PDI", "hPDI", "uPDI")) {
  ## 1. The "no-cells" model (NoCellModel): exposure + child sex + batch (20 SVs)
  assign(paste0("covs.NoCellModel.", my_exp), c(my_exp, "sex", paste0("sv", 1:20)))

  ## 2. The minimally adjusted model (MinModel): above + cell types
  assign(paste0("covs.MinModel.", my_exp), c(my_exp, "sex", paste0("sv", 1:20), cell.names))

  ## 3. The fully adjusted model (FullModel): above + maternal age + education + parity + smoking
  assign(paste0("covs.FullModel.", my_exp), c(my_exp, "sex", paste0("sv", 1:20), cell.names, "mat.age", "mat.edu", "mat.parity", "mat.smoking"))

  ## 4. The additional model (AddModel): above + maternal BMI + energy intake + dietary supplementation
  assign(paste0("covs.AddModel.", my_exp), c(my_exp, "sex", paste0("sv", 1:20), cell.names, "mat.age", "mat.edu", "mat.parity", "mat.smoking", "mat.bmi",
  "mat.kcal", "mat.suppl"))
}

# Load phenotype data including cell types

## [PLEASE CHANGE] Load phenotype data (named as "pheno") from the path where your phenotype data is stored
pheno <- readRDS("...")
dim(pheno) # Should be 38 variables; in ALSPAC, N = 835 (with both phenotype and methylation data)
# [NOTE: Variable/column names of the 38 variables:
#   - Sample ID (1): "sample.id"
#   - Food groups (18): "wholegrain", "fruit", "vegetable", "nut", "legume", "vegetableoil", "teacoffee", "fruitjuice", "refinedgrain", "potato", "sugarbeverage",
"sweetdessert", "animalfat", "dairy", "egg", "fishseafood", "meat", "misc.animal"
#   - Frequency of key food groups (4): "meat_freq", "fishseafood_freq", "egg_freq", "dairy_freq"
#   - Covariates (8): "sex", "mat.age", "mat.edu", "mat.parity", "mat.smoking", "mat.bmi", "mat.suppl", "mat.kcal"
#   - Cell types (7): "CD8T", "CD4T", "NK", "Bcell", "Mono", "Gran", "nRBC"

## Check phenotype data
for (i in 1:length(c("sample.id", traits.and.covariates, cell.names))) {
  print(ifelse(c("sample.id", traits.and.covariates, cell.names)[i] %in% colnames(pheno) == F,
    paste("Warning: The variable called", c("sample.id", traits.and.covariates, cell.names)[i], "is missing from pheno."),
    paste("OK: The variable called", c("sample.id", traits.and.covariates, cell.names)[i], "is present in pheno.")))
}

#-----#
#           Load & Prepare Methylation Data           #----
#-----#

# [PLEASE CHANGE] Load methylation data (named as "meth") from the path where your methylation data is stored
load("...")
meth <- as.matrix(norm.beta.random[, pheno$sample.id]) # Rename the methylation data, only keep the samples in pheno, and make sure it is a matrix
rm(norm.beta.random)

# [PLEASE CHANGE] Filter probes
# [NOTE: You can use your preferred methods for probe filtering.]
#####

```

Below shows as an example of how ALSPAC remove: 1) probes with high detection p-values, 2) probes on sex chromosomes, and 3) probes used as controls:

1) Probes with high detection p-values

Load detection p-values

```
load("...")
pvals <- as.matrix(detp[, pheno$sample.id]) # Rename the detection p-value data, only keep the samples in pheno, and make sure it is a matrix (similar to meth)
rm(detp)
```

Identify probes with high detection p-values

```
pvalue_over_0.05 <- pvals > 0.05
count_over_0.05 <- rowSums(sign(pvalue_over_0.05))
probes.to.exclude.p <- rownames(pvals)[which(count_over_0.05 > ncol(pvals) * 0.05)]
```

2) Probes on sex chromosomes

Extract annotation data using the "meffil" package (see package details at: <https://github.com/perishky/meffil>)

[PLEASE CHANGE] Please uncomment the code below if the required package has not been installed

```
# source("http://bioconductor.org/biocLite.R")
```

```
# install.packages("devtools") # If not already installed
```

```
# library(devtools)
```

```
# install_github("perishky/meffil")
```

```
library(meffil)
```

```
annotation <- meffil.get.features("450k")
```

Identify probes on sex chromosomes

```
XY <- as.character(annotation$name[which(annotation$chromosome %in% c("chrX", "chrY"))])
```

3) Probes used as controls

```
SNPs.and.controls <- as.character(annotation$name[-grep("cg|ch", annotation$name)])
```

Remove all above probes

```
print(paste("Before filtering, there were ", nrow(meth), " probes"))
```

```
annotation <- annotation[-which(annotation$name %in% c(probes.to.exclude.p, XY, SNPs.and.controls),)]
```

```
meth <- subset(meth, row.names(meth) %in% annotation$name)
```

```
print(paste("After filtering, there are now ", nrow(meth), " probes."))
```

```
print(paste(length(probes.to.exclude.p), " removed because they have a high detection p-value."))
```

```
print(paste(length(XY), " removed because they are on sex chromosomes."))
```

```
print(paste(length(SNPs.and.controls), " removed because they are controls."))
```

```
rm(pvalue_over_0.05, count_over_0.05, probes.to.exclude.p, XY, SNPs.and.controls, pvals)
```

```
#####
```

```
#-----#
```

```
#           Remove Outliers           #---
```

```
#-----#
```

Use the Tukey (IQR*3) method

[NOTE: Please skip this step if it has already been applied in your cohort data.]

```
log.iqr <- data.frame(cpgs = row.names(meth), NAs.before.IQR3 = rowSums(is.na(meth)))
```

```
meth <- IQR.removal(meth)
```

```
log.iqr$NAs.after.IQR3 <- rowSums(is.na(meth))
```

```
save(log.iqr, file = paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".logIQR.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".Rdata"))
```

```
#-----#
```

```
#           Generate Variables of Interest           #---
```

```
#-----#
```

"veggie1" & "veggie2" - Diet-based vegetarianism (vegetarian subgroups)

Data preparation: Generate weekly intake frequency (times/week) of meat & poultry, fish & seafood, egg, and dairy

[NOTE: Please do NOT add "na.rm = T" in rowSums below, otherwise all NAs will be classified as vegans.]

```
pheno$meatfish_freq <- rowSums(pheno[, c("meat_freq", "fishseafood_freq")]) # Meat & poultry + fish & seafood
```

```
pheno$eggdairy_freq <- rowSums(pheno[, c("egg_freq", "dairy_freq")]) # Egg + dairy
```

```
pheno$animal_freq <- rowSums(pheno[, c("meat_freq", "fishseafood_freq", "egg_freq", "dairy_freq")]) # Meat & poultry + fish & seafood + egg + dairy (all animal-based foods)
```

Vegetarian subgroups (detailed) - Coded from the least to the most restricted subgroup

0 - Non-vegetarian - meat & poultry: no restriction; fish & seafood: no restriction; egg & dairy: no restriction

```
pheno$VegDiet_subgroup <- 0
```

```
pheno$VegDiet_subgroup[is.na(pheno$meat_freq) | is.na(pheno$fishseafood_freq) | is.na(pheno$egg_freq) | is.na(pheno$dairy_freq)] <- NA
```

1 - Pesco-vegetarian - meat & poultry < 1 time/month (i.e., 0.25 time/week); fish & seafood >= 1 time/month; egg & dairy: no restriction

```
pheno$VegDiet_subgroup[pheno$meat_freq < 0.25 & pheno$fishseafood_freq >= 0.25] <- 1
```

2 - Lacto-ovo-vegetarian - meat & poultry + fish & seafood < 1 time/month; egg + dairy >= 1 time/month

```
pheno$VegDiet_subgroup[pheno$meatfish_freq < 0.25 & pheno$eggdairy_freq >= 0.25] <- 2
```

3 - Vegan - meat & poultry + fish & seafood + egg + dairy < 1 time/month

```
pheno$VegDiet_subgroup[pheno$animal_freq < 0.25] <- 3
```

```

## Vegetarian subgroups (combined into 3 categories) - Used for surrogate variable analysis below
### 0 - Non-vegetarian
### 1 - Pesco-vegetarian
### 2 - Full vegetarian (including lacto-ovo-vegetarian & vegan)
pheno$VegDiet_3cat <- NA
pheno$VegDiet_3cat[pheno$VegDiet_subgroup == 0] <- 0
pheno$VegDiet_3cat[pheno$VegDiet_subgroup == 1] <- 1
pheno$VegDiet_3cat[pheno$VegDiet_subgroup %in% c(2, 3)] <- 2

## Vegetarianism (binary)
### "veggie1": Full vegetarian vs. non-vegetarian
#### 0 - Non-vegetarian
#### 1 - Full vegetarian
#### [NOTE: In this exposure variable, all pesco-vegetarians are set as NAs.]
pheno$veggie1 <- NA
pheno$veggie1[pheno$VegDiet_3cat == 0] <- 0
pheno$veggie1[pheno$VegDiet_3cat == 2] <- 1

### "veggie2": Full vegetarian + pesco-vegetarian vs. non-vegetarian
#### 0 - Non-vegetarian
#### 1 - Full vegetarian + pesco-vegetarian
pheno$veggie2 <- NA
pheno$veggie2[pheno$VegDiet_3cat == 0] <- 0
pheno$veggie2[pheno$VegDiet_3cat %in% c(1, 2)] <- 1

#####

# PDI / hPDI / uPDI - Plant-based diet indices
# [NOTE: Please skip the whole section if your study is in tier 2 and DO NOT FORGET to remove the parts related to PDI/hPDI/uPDI in subsequent analyses.
# Tier 1 studies refer to those with data for BOTH "veggie1"/"veggie2" AND PDI/hPDI/uPDI analyses;
# Tier 2 studies refer to those with data for "veggie1"/"veggie2" analyses ONLY.]

## First keep complete cases only
## [NOTE: This step is VERY IMPORTANT, as we need to ensure that all tertiles are calculated in the final EWAS samples (i.e., complete cases).
## "veggie1" has more missing data than "veggie2", as it has dropped pesco-vegetarians.
## Here, we do NOT consider the missing data in "veggie1", but will address them later at the EWAS stage.
## In ALSPAC, N dropped from 835 (those with both phenotype and methylation data) to 687 (complete cases).]
pheno <- pheno[complete.cases(subset(pheno, select = -c(veggie1))), ]

## Check distribution of 18 food groups
food_group_name <- c("wholegrain", "fruit", "vegetable", "nut", "legume", "vegetableoil", "teacoffee", "fruitjuice", "refinedgrain", "potato", "sugarbeverage",
"sweetdessert", "animalfat", "dairy", "egg", "fishseafood", "meat", "misc.animal")

show_quantile_values <- function(var_name) {
  my_var <- pheno[, var_name]
  x <- quantile(my_var, probs = c(0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3, 0.333, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.667, 0.7, 0.75, 0.8, 0.9, 1), na.rm = T)
  y <- data.frame("Food_group" = var_name,
                 "N" = length(na.omit(my_var)),
                 `Min` = x[1], `P10` = x[2], `P20` = x[3], `P25` = x[4], `P30` = x[5],
                 `P33.3` = x[6], `P40` = x[7], `P50` = x[8], `P60` = x[9],
                 `P66.7` = x[10], `P70` = x[11], `P75` = x[12], `P80` = x[13], `P90` = x[14], `Max` = x[15])
  return(y)
}

food_group_distribute <- data.frame(matrix(ncol = 17, nrow = 0))

for (var_name in food_group_name) {
  x <- show_quantile_values(var_name)
  food_group_distribute <- rbind(food_group_distribute, x)
}

write.csv(food_group_distribute, paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".food.group.distribute.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".csv"), row.names = F)

## Set up functions for positive and negative scoring based on tertiles of each food group
## [NOTE: You may find some food groups in your data have very skewed distribution or do not have enough variation/granularity to calculate tertiles.
## For example, in ALSPAC, >33% of participants had no intake of nuts, vegetable oil, sugar-sweetened beverages, or miscellaneous animal food.
## The functions below automatically address this issue by:
## - If >33% of participants had no intake -
## 1) Set the first "tertile" to zero (i.e., the lowest intake in your data, which includes >33% of participants);
## 2) Then dividing the second and third "tertiles" using the median of the rest participants (i.e., those with non-zero intakes).
## - Otherwise - Use the standard method for tertile calculation.
## If you still fail to get tertiles (i.e., 3 relatively balanced categories) using the method provided, please get in touch.]

#### Positive scoring
p_score_3 <- function(var_name) {
  my_var <- pheno[, var_name]

  ##### First obtain the cutoffs for tertiles
  P0 <- min(my_var, na.rm = T)
  P33.3 <- quantile(my_var, probs = 0.333, na.rm = T)
  P66.7 <- quantile(my_var, probs = 0.667, na.rm = T)

```

```

P100 <- max(my_var, na.rm = T)

#### When >33.3% with the same lowest intake (most likely to be 0)
if (P0 == P33.3) {
  ##### Create a warning message and introduce the solution
  writeLines(paste0("Warning for ", var_name, ": >33.3% with the same lowest intake (", P0, "):\nSolution: Set all of the lowest as Q1, then take the median of the
rest to split Q2 and Q3."))

  ##### Modify the range of tertiles and assign positive scores (1-3)
  pheno[, "my_var_3"] <- NA # Create an empty column
  pheno[which(my_var == P0), "my_var_3"] <- 1 # Set all of those with the lowest intake as Q1
  pheno[which(my_var > P0 & my_var <= median(my_var[my_var > P0], na.rm = T)), "my_var_3"] <- 2 # For the rest, set those with intake <=median as Q2
  pheno[which(my_var > median(my_var[my_var > P0], na.rm = T)), "my_var_3"] <- 3 # And then set those with intake >median as Q3
  my_var_3 <- c(pheno[, "my_var_3"]) # Convert column into vector for subsequent combination
  pheno <- subset(pheno, select = -c(my_var_3)) # Remove the newly created column from the main dataset
}

#### In other situations - Take tertiles and assign positive scores
else {
  my_var_3 <- findInterval(my_var, c(-Inf, quantile(my_var, probs = c(0.333, 0.667), na.rm = T), Inf))
}

#### Return outputs
return(my_var_3)
}

### Negative scoring
r_score_3 <- function(var_name) {
  my_var_3 <- p_score_3(var_name) # Same as above for setting tertiles
  my_var_3 <- dplyr::recode(my_var_3, "1" = 3, "2" = 2, "3" = 1) # Recoded as reverse scores
  return(my_var_3)
}

## Apply function to create tertiles for each of the 18 food groups
for (var_name in food_group_name) {
  assign(paste0(var_name, "_3"), factor(p_score_3(var_name), label = c("T1", "T2", "T3")))
  pheno <- cbind(pheno, get(paste0(var_name, "_3")))
}
for (i in 1:18) {
  colnames(pheno)[ncol(pheno) - 18 + i] <- paste0(food_group_name[i], "_3") # Add 18 food group tertile variables (columns) to the end of pheno
}
head(pheno) # Tertile variables should have been added to the last 18 columns

## Set up functions for showing tertile cutoffs and generating descriptive table for the 18 food groups
tertile_cutoff <- function(var_name) {
  my_var <- pheno[, var_name]
  my_var_3 <- p_score_3(var_name)
  T1_lo <- round(min(my_var[my_var_3 == 1], na.rm = T), digits = 2)
  T1_up <- round(max(my_var[my_var_3 == 1], na.rm = T), digits = 2)
  T2_lo <- round(min(my_var[my_var_3 == 2], na.rm = T), digits = 2)
  T2_up <- round(max(my_var[my_var_3 == 2], na.rm = T), digits = 2)
  T3_lo <- round(min(my_var[my_var_3 == 3], na.rm = T), digits = 2)
  T3_up <- round(max(my_var[my_var_3 == 3], na.rm = T), digits = 2)
  x <- paste0("T1: ", T1_lo, "-", T1_up, " | T2: ", T2_lo, "-", T2_up, " | T3: ", T3_lo, "-", T3_up)
  return(x)
}

describe_food_group <- function(var_name) {
  x <- c(`Food group` = var_name,
        `Cutoffs` = tertile_cutoff(var_name),
        table(factor(p_score_3(var_name), label = c("T1", "T2", "T3")), useNA = "always"))
  return(x)
}

## Apply function to generate descriptive table for the 18 food groups
food_group_tertile <- data.frame(matrix(ncol = 6, nrow = 0))
for (var_name in food_group_name) {
  x <- describe_food_group(var_name)
  food_group_tertile <- rbind(food_group_tertile, x)
}
colnames(food_group_tertile) <- c("Food_group", "Cutoffs", "N_T1", "N_T2", "N_T3", "N_missing")
write.csv(food_group_tertile, paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".food.group.tertile.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".csv"), row.names = F)

## Apply functions to calculate PDIs

### Overall plant-based diet index (PDI)
pheno$PDI <-
  ##### 7 healthy plant food groups assigned positive scores
  p_score_3("wholegrain") + p_score_3("fruit") + p_score_3("vegetable") + p_score_3("nut") + p_score_3("legume") + p_score_3("vegetableoil") +
  p_score_3("teacoffee") +
  ##### 5 less healthy plant food groups assigned positive scores
  p_score_3("fruitjuice") + p_score_3("refinedgrain") + p_score_3("potato") + p_score_3("sugarbeverage") + p_score_3("sweetdessert") +
  ##### 6 animal food groups assigned reverse scores

```

```

r_score_3("animalfat") + r_score_3("dairy") + r_score_3("egg") + r_score_3("fishseafood") + r_score_3("meat") + r_score_3("misc.animal")

### Healthful plant-based diet index (hPDI)
pheno$hPDI <-
  ##### 7 healthy plant food groups assigned positive scores
  p_score_3("wholegrain") + p_score_3("fruit") + p_score_3("vegetable") + p_score_3("nut") + p_score_3("legume") + p_score_3("vegetableoil") +
  p_score_3("teacoffee") +
  ##### 5 less healthy plant food groups assigned reverse scores
  r_score_3("fruitjuice") + r_score_3("refinedgrain") + r_score_3("potato") + r_score_3("sugarbeverage") + r_score_3("sweetdessert") +
  ##### 6 animal food groups assigned reverse scores
  r_score_3("animalfat") + r_score_3("dairy") + r_score_3("egg") + r_score_3("fishseafood") + r_score_3("meat") + r_score_3("misc.animal")

### Unhealthful plant-based diet index (uPDI)
pheno$uPDI <-
  ##### 7 healthy plant food groups assigned reverse scores
  r_score_3("wholegrain") + r_score_3("fruit") + r_score_3("vegetable") + r_score_3("nut") + r_score_3("legume") + r_score_3("vegetableoil") +
  r_score_3("teacoffee") +
  ##### 5 less healthy plant food groups assigned positive scores
  p_score_3("fruitjuice") + p_score_3("refinedgrain") + p_score_3("potato") + p_score_3("sugarbeverage") + p_score_3("sweetdessert") +
  ##### 6 animal food groups assigned reverse scores
  r_score_3("animalfat") + r_score_3("dairy") + r_score_3("egg") + r_score_3("fishseafood") + r_score_3("meat") + r_score_3("misc.animal")

## Histograms of PDI/hPDI/uPDI
for (my_exp in c("PDI", "hPDI", "uPDI")) {
  jpeg(paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".", my_exp, ".histogram.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".jpg"))
  hist(pheno[, my_exp], main = paste0("Histogram of ", my_exp, " (N = ", sum(is.na(pheno[, my_exp]) == F), ")"), xlab = my_exp)
  dev.off()
}

#-----#
#           Generate Surrogate Variables           #----
#-----#

# [NOTE: For consistency, we highly recommend all cohorts use surrogate variable analysis (SVA) to adjust for batch.
# The code below will generate 20 surrogate variables (SVs) reflecting systematic variations in methylation data caused by unknown/unmodeled/latent sources
of noise.
# These SVs will be included as covariates in EWAS models to remove the impact from batch effects.
# Please note that SVA is a COMPLETE CASE ANALYSIS and does NOT allow any missing data in the input files.
# See details about SVA at https://rdrr.io/bioc/sva/f/inst/doc/sva.pdf.
# If you do not think SVA is applicable to your data, or if you prefer using methods other than/in addition to SVA (e.g., ComBat), please get in touch.]

# Prepare data

## Phenotype data - Keep complete cases and key variables
sva.pheno <- na.omit(pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% c("sample.id", "VegDiet_3cat", covs.AddModel.PDI, covs.AddModel.hPDI, covs.AddModel.uPDI)])
dim(sva.pheno) # Sample size will not change if you have already subset to complete cases at the beginning of PDI calculation above

## Methylation data - Recode missing values
sva.meth <- meth[, match(sva.pheno$sample.id, colnames(meth))] # Match with sample IDs in pheno
k <- which(is.na(sva.meth), arr.ind = T) # Find indices of NAs
sva.meth[k] <- rowMedians(sva.meth, na.rm = T)[k[, 1]] # Replace NAs with the row median

## Generate the full model matrix (includes all adjustment variables and exposure variables of interest)
## [NOTE: Here we generate 1 set of 20 SVs for all 5 exposure variables.
## To avoid including missing data in veggie1 (pesco-vegetarians set as NAs), we use the 3-category vegetarian subgroup variable ("VegDiet_3cat") to
combine the information in veggie1 and veggie2.]
mod <- model.matrix(reformulate(paste0("sva.pheno$", colnames(sva.pheno)[which(colnames(sva.pheno) %in% c("VegDiet_3cat", covs.AddModel.PDI,
covs.AddModel.hPDI, covs.AddModel.uPDI)]))))

## Generate the null model matrix (contains only the adjustment variables)
mod0 <- mod[, -which(colnames(mod) %in% c("sva.pheno$VegDiet_3cat", "sva.pheno$PDI", "sva.pheno$hPDI", "sva.pheno$uPDI"))]

# Run SVA
# [NOTE: Troubleshooting tips:
# - If you see the error message "Error in eigen(t(resid) %*% resid) : infinite or missing values in 'x'",
# please make sure that all columns in sva.meth have been matched with sample.id in sva.pheno with the same order.
# - If you see the error message "Error in solve.default(t(mod) %*% mod) : Lapack routine dgesv: system is exactly singular: U[19,19] = 0",
# please make sure that your input files (sva.meth, mod, mod0) do not have any missing data or duplicated columns.
# Please get in touch if you have any difficulties running SVA.
sva.res <- sva(sva.meth, mod = mod, mod0 = mod0, n.sv = 20)

# Combine data
SVs <- as.data.frame(sva.res$sv)
colnames(SVs) <- paste0("sv", 1:ncol(SVs)) # 20 SVs named as sv1-sv20
SVs$sample.id <- sva.pheno$sample.id
pheno <- merge(pheno, SVs, by = "sample.id") # [NOTE: This step should NOT reduce the sample size, as we have already subset the data to complete cases.]
saveRDS(pheno, paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".pheno.SV.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".rds"))

#-----#
#           Match & Check           #----
#-----#

# Include identical individuals in pheno and meth files

```

```

common <- intersect(colnames(meth), pheno$sample.id)
pheno2 <- pheno[pheno$sample.id %in% common, ]
sum(is.na(pheno2[, colnames(pheno2) != "veggie1"])) # Should be 0 (i.e., no missing data in all variables except for "veggie1")
meth2 <- meth[, (match(pheno2$sample.id, colnames(meth)))]

# Double check

## Question 1: Are the number of samples identical between pheno2 and meth2 - Should be YES
if (!dim(pheno2)[1] == dim(meth2)[2]) {
  print("Warning: The number of individuals NOT identical between pheno2 and meth2 - PLEASE FIX")
} else {
  print("OK: The SAME number of individuals in pheno2 and meth2 - PLEASE CONTINUE")
}

## Question 2: Are pheno2 and meth2 ordered in the same way? - Should be YES
if (!identical(as.character(pheno2$sample.id), as.character(colnames(meth2)))) {
  print("Warning: Ordering of meth2 and pheno2 NOT identical, or variable type (factor vs, character?) NOT matched - PLEASE CHECK AND FIX")
} else {
  print("OK: Individuals in the SAME order in pheno2 and meth2 - PLEASE CONTINUE")
}

## Question 3: Is meth2 a matrix? - Should be YES
if (!is.matrix(meth2)) {
  print("Warning: meth2 is NOT a matrix - PLEASE FIX VIA: meth2 <- as.matrix(meth2)")
} else {
  print("OK: meth2 is a matrix - PLEASE CONTINUE")
}

## Question 4: Is pheno2 a data frame? - Should be YES
if (!is.data.frame(pheno2)) {
  print("Warning: pheno2 is NOT a dataframe - PLEASE FIX VIA: pheno2 <- as.data.frame(pheno2)")
} else {
  print("OK: pheno2 is a dataframe - PLEASE CONTINUE")
}

# Rename for subsequent analyses
pheno <- pheno2
meth <- meth2
rm(pheno2, meth2)

#-----#
#           EWAS Analyses           #----#
#-----#

# Run EWASes for each exposure variable

## "veggie1" (full vegetarian vs. non-vegetarian)
## [NOTE: We need to generate separate datasets for this exposure variable to remove missing data (pesco-vegetarians).]
pheno2 <- pheno[-which(is.na(pheno$veggie1)), ] # Keep complete cases for "veggie1" (in ALSPAC, N further dropped from 687 to 666), otherwise an error will
meth2 <- meth[, (match(pheno2$sample.id, colnames(meth)))]
identical(pheno2$sample.id, colnames(meth2)) # Should be TRUE

ewas.res.NoCellModel.veggie1 <- ewas.function(meth2, pheno2[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.NoCellModel.veggie1], variable.of.interest = "veggie1")
ewas.res.MinModel.veggie1 <- ewas.function(meth2, pheno2[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.MinModel.veggie1], variable.of.interest = "veggie1")
ewas.res.FullModel.veggie1 <- ewas.function(meth2, pheno2[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.FullModel.veggie1], variable.of.interest = "veggie1")
ewas.res.AddModel.veggie1 <- ewas.function(meth2, pheno2[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.AddModel.veggie1], variable.of.interest = "veggie1")

save(list = intersect(ls(), c("ewas.res.NoCellModel.veggie1", "ewas.res.MinModel.veggie1", "ewas.res.FullModel.veggie1", "ewas.res.AddModel.veggie1")),
file = paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".veggie1.EWASres.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".Rdata"))

## "veggie2" (full vegetarian + pesco-vegetarian vs. non-vegetarian)
ewas.res.NoCellModel.veggie2 <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.NoCellModel.veggie2], variable.of.interest = "veggie2")
ewas.res.MinModel.veggie2 <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.MinModel.veggie2], variable.of.interest = "veggie2")
ewas.res.FullModel.veggie2 <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.FullModel.veggie2], variable.of.interest = "veggie2")
ewas.res.AddModel.veggie2 <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.AddModel.veggie2], variable.of.interest = "veggie2")

save(list = intersect(ls(), c("ewas.res.NoCellModel.veggie2", "ewas.res.MinModel.veggie2", "ewas.res.FullModel.veggie2", "ewas.res.AddModel.veggie2")),
file = paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".veggie2.EWASres.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".Rdata"))

## PDI
ewas.res.NoCellModel.PDI <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.NoCellModel.PDI], variable.of.interest = "PDI")
ewas.res.MinModel.PDI <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.MinModel.PDI], variable.of.interest = "PDI")
ewas.res.FullModel.PDI <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.FullModel.PDI], variable.of.interest = "PDI")
ewas.res.AddModel.PDI <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.AddModel.PDI], variable.of.interest = "PDI")

save(list = intersect(ls(), c("ewas.res.NoCellModel.PDI", "ewas.res.MinModel.PDI", "ewas.res.FullModel.PDI", "ewas.res.AddModel.PDI")),
file = paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".PDI.EWASres.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".Rdata"))

## hPDI
ewas.res.NoCellModel.hPDI <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.NoCellModel.hPDI], variable.of.interest = "hPDI")
ewas.res.MinModel.hPDI <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.MinModel.hPDI], variable.of.interest = "hPDI")
ewas.res.FullModel.hPDI <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.FullModel.hPDI], variable.of.interest = "hPDI")

```

```

ewas.res.AddModel.hPDI <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.AddModel.hPDI], variable.of.interest = "hPDI")

save(list = intersect(ls(), c("ewas.res.NoCellModel.hPDI", "ewas.res.MinModel.hPDI", "ewas.res.FullModel.hPDI", "ewas.res.AddModel.hPDI")),
file = paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".hPDI.EWASres.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".Rdata"))

## uPDI
ewas.res.NoCellModel.uPDI <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.NoCellModel.uPDI], variable.of.interest = "uPDI")
ewas.res.MinModel.uPDI <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.MinModel.uPDI], variable.of.interest = "uPDI")
ewas.res.FullModel.uPDI <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.FullModel.uPDI], variable.of.interest = "uPDI")
ewas.res.AddModel.uPDI <- ewas.function(meth, pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% covs.AddModel.uPDI], variable.of.interest = "uPDI")

save(list = intersect(ls(), c("ewas.res.NoCellModel.uPDI", "ewas.res.MinModel.uPDI", "ewas.res.FullModel.uPDI", "ewas.res.AddModel.uPDI")),
file = paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".uPDI.EWASres.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".Rdata"))

#-----#
#           Descriptive Results           #----#
#-----#

# Table 1 - Summary statistics of phenotypes
tableone <- as.data.frame(print(CreateTableOne(
data = pheno[, colnames(pheno) %in% c("sample.id", "veggie1", "veggie2")], # Keep "VegDiet_3cat" only for vegetarian subgroups
factorVars = c("VegDiet_subgroup", "VegDiet_3cat", "sex", "mat.edu", "mat.parity", "mat.smoking", "mat.suppl"),
test = F)))

write.csv(tableone, paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".tableone.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".csv"), row.names = T)

# Intakes of the 18 food groups and PDIs by vegetarian subgroups
# [NOTE: You still need to generate this table even if your study is in tier 2 (please remove the variables not available in your study from below).]
table_by_VegDiet <- as.data.frame(print(CreateTableOne(
data = subset(pheno, select = c("wholegrain", "fruit", "vegetable", "nut", "legume",
"vegetableoil", "teacoffee", "fruitjuice", "refinedgrain", "potato",
"sugarbeverage", "sweetdessert", "animalfat", "dairy", "egg",
"fishseafood", "meat", "misc.animal", "PDI", "hPDI", "uPDI", "VegDiet_subgroup")),
vars = c("wholegrain", "fruit", "vegetable", "nut", "legume",
"vegetableoil", "teacoffee", "fruitjuice", "refinedgrain", "potato",
"sugarbeverage", "sweetdessert", "animalfat", "dairy", "egg",
"fishseafood", "meat", "misc.animal", "PDI", "hPDI", "uPDI"),
strata = "VegDiet_subgroup"),
test = F))

write.csv(table_by_VegDiet, paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".ByVegDiet.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".csv"), row.names = T)

# Correlation matrix between PDIs and intakes of the 18 food groups
correlogram <- GGally::ggcorr(data = subset(pheno, select = c("misc.animal", "meat", "fishseafood", "egg", "dairy",
"animalfat", "sweetdessert", "sugarbeverage", "potato", "refinedgrain",
"fruitjuice", "teacoffee", "vegetableoil", "legume", "nut",
"vegetable", "fruit", "wholegrain", "uPDI", "hPDI", "PDI")),
method = c("pairwise", "pearson"), label = T, label_alpha = T, label_round = 2)

ggplot2::ggsave(correlogram, file = paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".correlogram.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".png"), height = 16, width = 18)

#-----#
#           Q-Q Plots & Lambdas           #----#
#-----#

# Generate Q-Q plots
model_list <- c("NoCellModel.veggie1", "MinModel.veggie1", "FullModel.veggie1", "AddModel.veggie1",
"NoCellModel.veggie2", "MinModel.veggie2", "FullModel.veggie2", "AddModel.veggie2",
"NoCellModel.PDI", "MinModel.PDI", "FullModel.PDI", "AddModel.PDI",
"NoCellModel.hPDI", "MinModel.hPDI", "FullModel.hPDI", "AddModel.hPDI",
"NoCellModel.uPDI", "MinModel.uPDI", "FullModel.uPDI", "AddModel.uPDI")

for (my_mod in model_list) {
my_res <- get(paste0("ewas.res.", my_mod))
jpeg(file = paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".", my_mod, ".QQ.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".jpg"))
qq(my_res$p)
dev.off()
}

# Calculate lambdas
lambda_cal <- function(my_mod) {
my_res <- get(paste0("ewas.res.", my_mod))
lambda <- median(qchisq(my_res$p, df = 1, lower.tail = F), na.rm = T) / qchisq(0.5, 1)
x <- c(my_mod, lambda)
return(x)
}

lambda_res <- data.frame(matrix(ncol = 2, nrow = 0))
for (my_mod in model_list) {
x <- lambda_cal(my_mod)
lambda_res <- rbind(lambda_res, x)
}
colnames(lambda_res) <- c("Model", "Lambda")

```

```
write.csv(lambda_res, paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".lambda.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".csv"), row.names = F)
```

```
#-----#  
#           Differentially Methylated Regions (DMR)           #----  
#-----#
```

```
# Loop through all models and exposure variables to run DMR analysis  
for (my_mod in c("NoCellModel", "MinModel", "FullModel", "AddModel")) {  
  for (my_exp in c("veggie1", "veggie2", "PDI", "hPDI", "uPDI")) {  
    ## Set up input data  
    stats <- get(paste0("ewas.res.", my_mod, ".", my_exp))  
    ifelse(my_exp == "veggie1", betas <- meth2, betas <- meth) # meth2 (i.e., meth excluding pesco-vegetarians) was used for "veggie1" EWAS above  
  
    ## Match genome annotation  
    annotation <- meffil::meffil.get.features("450k")  
    annotation <- annotation[match(rownames(betas), annotation$name), ]  
    order.idx <- order(annotation$chromosome, annotation$position)  
    betas <- betas[order.idx, ]  
    annotation <- annotation[order.idx, ]  
    stats <- stats[order.idx, ]  
  
    ## Run DMR analysis  
    dmr.res <- dmrff(estimate = stats$coef, se = stats$se, p.value = stats$p, methylation = betas, chr = annotation$chromosome, pos = annotation$position, maxgap = 500, verbose = T)  
  
    ## Select and save top findings  
    dmr.res <- dmr.res[which(dmr.res$p.adjust < 0.05 & dmr.res$n > 1), ]  
    print(dmr.res)  
    write.csv(dmr.res, paste0("MatVegDiet.", study, ".", my_mod, ".", my_exp, ".dmr.", timepoint, ".", analysis.date, ".csv"), row.names = F)  
  }  
}
```

```
#-----#  
#           Output List           #----  
#-----#
```

```
# Lastly, please check if you have produced the following output files in the specified formats:  
# - Rdata files (5 for tier 1 studies, 2 for tier 2 studies) for EWAS results  
# - Each contains outputs from all four EWAS models for one exposure variable  
# - Named as: "MatVegDiet.[study].[my_exp].EWASres.[timepoint].[analysis.date].Rdata"  
# - One Rdata files for the log of the IQR*3 (Tukey) method  
# - Named as: "MatVegDiet.[study].logIQR.[timepoint].[analysis.date].Rdata"  
# - One csv file showing the distribution of the 18 food groups  
# - Named as: "MatVegDiet.[study].food.group.distribute.[timepoint].[analysis.date].csv"  
# - Not applicable for tier 2 studies  
# - One csv file showing the tertile cutoffs of the 18 food groups  
# - Named as: "MatVegDiet.[study].food.group.tertile.[timepoint].[analysis.date].csv"  
# - Not applicable for tier 2 studies  
# - One csv file showing summary statistics of phenotype data  
# - Named as: "MatVegDiet.[study].tableone.[timepoint].[analysis.date].csv"  
# - One csv file showing the intake of each available food group by vegetarian subgroups  
# - Named as: "MatVegDiet.[study].ByVegDiet.[timepoint].[analysis.date].csv"  
# - One correlogram showing the correlation matrix between PDIs and intakes of the 18 food groups  
# - Named as: "MatVegDiet.[study].correlogram.[timepoint].[analysis.date].png"  
# - Not applicable for tier 2 studies  
# - Three histograms for PDI, hPDI, and uPDI  
# - Named as: "MatVegDiet.[study].[my_exp].histogram.[timepoint].[analysis.date].jpg"  
# - Not applicable for tier 2 studies  
# - Q-Q plots (20 for tier 1 studies, 8 for tier 2 studies)  
# - Separate plots will be created for each exposure variable and model  
# - Named as: "MatVegDiet.[study].[MODEL].[my_exp].QQ.[timepoint].[analysis.date].jpg"  
# - One csv file showing lambdas for all EWAS models  
# - Named as: "MatVegDiet.[study].lambda.[timepoint].[analysis.date].csv"  
# - csv files (20 for tier 1 studies, 8 for tier 2 studies) for DMR results  
# - Based on the fully adjusted model for each exposure variable  
# - Named as: "MatVegDiet.[study].[my_exp].dmr.[timepoint].[analysis.date].csv"  
  
# Please do not forget to complete and return the Excel file named "MatVegDiet.[STUDY].cohortinfo.xlsx" (including 2 tabs).  
  
# Massive thanks for your contribution!
```